

Comparison of Different Approaches for the Calculation of the Integrated Zone and the Cross-over Value in Amplitude Sweep Tests

Christoph Haas¹, Pia Heibach², Patricia Pértile³,
Dörthe Holthusen⁴, Rainer Horn¹

¹*Institute for Plant Nutrition and Soil Science, CAU Kiel,
Hermann-Rodewald-Str. 2, 24118 Kiel, Germany*

²*Hanse-Agro – Beratung und Entwicklung GmbH, Kirchstr.
14a, 24214 Gettorf, Germany*

³*Soils Department, Universidade Federal de Santa Maria
(UFSM), Av. Roraima 1000, Santa Maria – RS, CEP: 97105-
900, Brazil*

⁴*Department of Vegetation Studies, Landscape Management,
Federal Institute of Hydrology, Am Mainzer Tor 1, 56068
Koblenz, Germany.*

Corresponding Author: Christoph Haas, e-mail: C.Haas@soils.uni-kiel.de

Received: 7 October 2021

Accepted: 23 October 2021

Abstract

In soil rheology, the amplitude sweep test (AST) simulates dynamic stresses by means of either increasing shear strain or shear stress and returns information on the viscoelasticity and shear resistance of soils. The dimensionless Integral Z, I_z , is used to compare the microstructural soil stability, based upon the loss factor, $\tan \delta$. Sandy, silty, loamy, and clayey topsoil-samples, equilibrated to defined matric potentials, were subjected to ASTs and pedotransfer functions were derived to test the suitability of soil physical and chemical parameters to estimate the value of I_z . The current approach to the calculation of I_z and of the shear strain and stress values at the cross-over (CO, i.e., where the storage modulus (G') equals the loss modulus (G'')) on the base of the commercial software *RheoPlus* was found to be unprecise due to data simplifications and varying assumptions regarding data interpolation. The deviation of the values at the CO and of I_z of the two calculation methods was evaluated. Considering 132 soil samples, I_z values ranged from 6.8 to 79.4, and the mean value and standard deviation of the difference between the values of I_z as calculated by *RheoPlus* and those calculated as defined by Markgraf et al. (2009) were 0.78 and 1.49, respectively. No difference was found for soil samples with loss factor values smaller than 1 in the complete strain range. A neglectable difference was found for most samples because the loss factor values behind the 'cross-over' were close to 1 and not significantly altered when set to 1. The results underline, that despite the simplifications that were made for the calculations of the rheological parameter, the resulting values of most of the considered samples, do not differ in an unacceptable manner. For the considered soils and matric potentials, the derived pedotransfer functions are applicable to estimate the values of I_z from soil chemical and

physical properties such as the soil matric potential, and sand, clay, and soil organic carbon contents.

Keywords: Rheology; Rheometry; Integral Z; AST

Introduction

The mechanical soil stability is controlled by interactions of biological, chemical and physical processes at smaller scales, such as the exudation of biological substances by plant roots and soil microbes, cementing of primary particles by chalk, and the shrink-swell induced development of soil aggregates by water-menisci forces. The aggregate stability, in turn, depends on the aggregate size (Tisdall and Oades, 1982), and is supposed to be stronger in smaller aggregates. Exceeding the soil stability by mechanical loading and shearing results in plastic deformation and the destruction of soil aggregates which define the pore space volumes, results in soil homogenization, and includes the loss of soil functions, such as the water storage and infiltration, and the trafficability of soils (Riggert et al. 2017).

Rheometry is a technique for characterising soil flow behaviour and the soil microstructural stability by applying small strains to small soil volumes. Intensive research has been done concerning the flow behaviour of clay suspensions as affected by pH, particle concentration, temperature (Brandenburg and Lagaly, 1988), organic matter content, salt concentration, ionic strength, type of cation present (Tombácz et al., 1989 and 2004), and clay mineralogy (Au and Leong, 2013). In the last two decades, rheometry was increasingly applied for the investigation of natural soils (Torrance, 1999; Ghezzehei and Or, 2001; Markgraf et al., 2006) and the effect of the aforementioned and of additional physical and chemical soil properties was investigated, e.g., water content, contents of electrolytes (Holthusen et al., 2010; Markgraf and Horn, 2006), organic matter (Khaidapova et al., 2016; Pértile et al., 2018), organic exudates in terms of model substances (Haas et al. 2018a), clay mineralogy (Baumgarten et al., 2013), or particle size distribution (Markgraf and Horn, 2006; Stoppe, 2015), and the applied vertical stress (Holthusen et al., 2017). In amplitude sweep tests (ASTs) increasing shear strains are applied to small soil volumes. The derived values of the storage (G') and loss (G'') moduli represent the soil flow behaviour in terms of an elastic and a plastic deformation component, respectively. The flow behaviour can be distinguished into three phases: (i) with small shear strains, the linear viscoelastic range is parameterised, which is characterised by elastic soil deformation. The soil deformation is reversible and no significant soil structural and functional changes are expected (Haas et al., 2016), and (ii) with intermediate shear strains, elastic prevails plastic/viscous behaviours, and (iii) with shear strains larger than those applied at the cross-over of G' and G'' , viscous prevails over elastic soil deformation behaviour, a soil structural breakdown occurs, and the pore system is irreversibly altered resulting in a loss of soil functions (Haas et al., 2016). The Integral z , I_z , was introduced by Markgraf and Horn (2009) as a summarising parameter of the loss factor (i.e., G''/G' ; $\tan \delta$) vs. shear strain relationship. The value is calculated by integrating the area between one and the $\tan \delta$ -values as a function of the applied shear strains with a lower (i.e., shear strain equal to 0.001%) and an upper integration limit (i.e., the shear strain at which the CO occurs) (Fig 2, dotted areas). This dimensionless, semi-quantitative parameter represents the quasi-elasticity of the soil and is used to quantify the stiffness degradation of soils (Batistão et al. 2020; Haas et al. 2018a; Holthusen et al., 2017, 2019, 2020; Khaidapova et al.

2016; Markgraf and Horn 2009; Markgraf et al. 2012; Stoppe and Horn, 2018; Stoppe 2015; Pértile et al., 2016; Pértile et al., 2018), and to identify single stages of thixotropy in allophanic Andosols (Baumgarten et al., 2013).

I_z often is calculated with the rheometer-inherent software *RheoPlus* (*RHEOPLUS/32 V3.21*, Anton Paar, Stuttgart, Germany), following the same calculation steps first conditioned by Markgraf and Horn (2009). However, as found by Haas (2018), Haas et al. (2018a), the measured data are changed within the calculation, and the integration limits are neglected resulting in inaccurate values for the integral Z . Furthermore, an automatic interpolation routine was activated by the software *RheoPlus* for the calculation of the shear strain and stress values at the cross-over of G' and G'' . Based on an unknown program-based decision tree, the data were transformed to linear and/or logarithmic scales. Unfortunately, in studies where values of I_z were published, the exact settings of the software have not been reported in detail (e.g., Markgraf and Horn 2009; Holthusen et al. 2017; Heibach et al., 2018; Stoppe and Horn, 2017; 2018). In this way, it can be assumed that all studies followed the same calculation steps first conditioned by Markgraf and Horn (2009). The error nor its magnitude has never been evaluated.

The objectives of this work are to investigate the error and its magnitude for different soils and soil conditions, and to test if pedotransfer functions are suitable to estimate the method-based difference of the absolute values of I_z and of the shear strains at which the cross-over occurs, and to derive pedotransfer functions to estimate the absolute values on the base of easily available soil parameters like the soil texture and the water-filled pore space. We hypothesised that the parameter values are influenced by the calculation methods due to data simplifications and modifications and that the resulting differences and the absolute values can be estimated from physical and chemical soil properties with the developed pedotransfer functions.

Theoretical Background: Amplitude sweep test and data evaluation

Most of the aforementioned studies with natural soils employed a rheometer with a 2.5 cm profiled parallel plate measuring system and conducted an amplitude sweep test (AST) with controlled shear strain. Here, the sample to be tested was enclosed between a fixed lower plate and the upper plate which is moving in an oscillating (i.e., clock- and counter-clockwise) manner with increasing amplitude at a constant frequency of 0.5 Hz. The shear strain applied via the deflection of the upper plate and the torque M needed to achieve the desired strain, is used to calculate the averaged shear stress applied, τ_a , according to Eq. 1 (Mezger, 2012).

$$\tau_a = \frac{2M}{\pi r^3} \quad (\text{Eq. 1})$$

with radius, r , of the oscillating upper plate. The shear strain, γ , is implemented in a sinusoidal pattern (Fig. 1a) which changes with time due to the oscillating movement of the upper plate and its increasing amplitude (see Fig. 1b). Depending on the deformation behaviour of the measured substance, the ‘immediateness’ of its reaction to the deflection of the oscillating upper plate is detected by the rheometer as the phase shift angle, δ , between the applied deformation and the response (i.e., the shear stress wave) of the soil sample. The observed responses (Fig. 1a) include the perfectly elastic response with δ equal to 0° ,

perfectly viscous behaviour with δ equal to 90° , and the soil typical (Markgraf and Horn, 2006) viscoelastic behaviour with δ larger than 0° and smaller than 90° .

Fig. 1. a) Flow behaviours as determinable with amplitude sweep tests (ASTs). The sinusoidal pattern of the applied deformation (grey and solid line) and the responses of the sample in case of a perfectly elastic sample (black and solid line, with δ equal to 0°), viscoelastic sample (dotted line, with δ larger than 0° and smaller than 90°), and perfect viscosity (dashed line, δ equal to 90°). Here, a constant amplitude is assumed, while the actual course of the deformation during AST is depicted in b).

For soil samples and low shear strains, the elastic deformation prevails the plastic deformation with δ smaller than 45° . From given values of γ and the resulting values of τ as well as δ , the storage modulus, G' , and loss modulus, G'' , can be derived with Eq. 2-3 (Mezger, 2012).

$$G' = \frac{\tau_a}{\gamma} \cos \delta \quad (\text{Eq. 2})$$

$$G'' = \frac{\tau_a}{\gamma} \sin \delta \quad (\text{Eq. 3})$$

G' is a measure of the elasticity of the soil, representing the energy that is available to reverse the gradual increase of soil deformation, G'' equals the dissipated energy (Mezger, 2012). The relation G''/G' is defined as loss factor, $\tan \delta$.

Throughout the further experiments in recent years, I_z was calculated by Haas (2018), Haas et al. (2018a), and Holthusen et al. (2020) directly from raw data using another software than *RheoPlus* and as described by Eq. 4 (Markgraf and Horn, 2009).

$$I_z = \int_{0.001\%}^{\text{cross-over}(\%)} (1 - \tan \delta) d\gamma \quad (\text{Eq. 4})$$

The studies by Haas (2018) and Haas et al. (2018a) noted that the *RheoPlus* software miscalculates the integrated area by setting values of $\tan \delta > 1$ to equal to 1, changing the slope of the $\tan \delta$ vs shear strain relationship (Figs. 2 a-b). In our own data analysis, we have found additionally, that the integration is not limited to the strain value at which the cross-over of G' and G'' occurs as right-hand limit as defined by Eq. 4 (Fig. 2a and Table 1), instead data points where $\tan \delta > 1$ are included even beyond the cross-over as described by Eq. 5.

$$I_z^+ = \int_{0.001\%}^{100\%} (1 - \tan \delta) d\gamma \quad (\text{Eq. 5})$$

with $\tan \delta$ larger than 1 set to equal 1.

Fig. 2. Measured loss factors (squares), $\tan \delta$, as a function of the shear strain, γ , used to calculate the value of the Integral Z, I_z , and $\tan \delta$ values as used to calculate the value of the Integral Z, I_z^+ , in the RheoPlus software (circles) of a) the sandy soil sample with the maximum deviation, and b) the sample with the second largest deviation between I_z^+ and I_z . The dotted areas represent I_z as defined by Eq. 4 and as calculated with the attached R-script. The dotted and the hatched areas jointly represent I_z^+ as calculated with RheoPlus. See also Table 1 for the detailed calculations for the sample shown in Fig. 2a).

The shear strain at the cross-over of G' and G'' was then calculated by interpolating measured values in accordance with the detected scaling of the automatic interpolation routine, as described by Eqs. 6-9.

$$G' + a_1 \gamma = G'' + a_2 \gamma \quad (\text{Eq. 6})$$

$$\log_{10}(G') + a_1 \log_{10}(\gamma) = \log_{10}(G'') + a_2 \log_{10}(\gamma) \quad (\text{Eq. 7})$$

$$\log_{10}(G') + a_1 \gamma = \log_{10}(G'') + a_2 \gamma \quad (\text{Eq. 8})$$

$$G' + a_1 \log_{10}(\gamma) = G'' + a_2 \log_{10}(\gamma) \quad (\text{Eq. 9})$$

with coefficients a_1 , and a_2 . The possible interpolation routines alter the values of the shear strain and of G' at the cross-over (Figs. 3 a) to d)).

Table 1. Measurement points, MP, shear strain, γ (%), loss factor, $\tan \delta$, of example data (Fig. 2) and derived values of segments of I_z^+ and I_z by linearly interpolation between the MP. Note: γ and $\tan \delta$ were rounded to four digits.

MP	γ (%)	$\tan \delta$	n	$I_z(n)$	$I_z^+(n)$
1	0.0001				
2	0.0002				
3	0.0003				
4	0.0004				
5	0.0007				
I1	0.0010	0.1237			
6	0.0011	0.1159	1	0.0001	0.0001
7	0.0017	0.1092	2	0.0006	0.0006
8	0.0028	0.1123	3	0.0009	0.0009
9	0.0045	0.1138	4	0.0015	0.0015
10	0.0073	0.1204	5	0.0024	0.0024
11	0.0117	0.1230	6	0.0039	0.0039
12	0.0189	0.1332	7	0.0062	0.0062
13	0.0304	0.1480	8	0.0099	0.0099
14	0.0489	0.1693	9	0.0156	0.0156
15	0.0788	0.1943	10	0.0244	0.0244
16	0.1269	0.2331	11	0.0378	0.0378
17	0.2043	0.2720	12	0.0579	0.0579
18	0.3290	0.3060	13	0.0887	0.0887
19	0.5297	0.3378	14	0.1361	0.1361
20	0.8529	0.3493	15	0.2122	0.2122
21	1.3730	0.3768	16	0.3313	0.3313
22	2.2110	0.3979	17	0.5134	0.5134
23	3.5610	0.4204	18	0.7976	0.7976
24	5.7340	0.4046	19	1.2766	1.2766
25	9.2350	0.4859	20	1.9422	1.9422
26	14.8700	0.8251	21	1.9413	1.9413
27	23.9500	0.8648	22	1.4079	1.4079
I2	25.3083	1.0000	23	0.0918	-
28	38.5500	2.3180		-	0.9870
29	62.0900	0.6919		-	3.6263
30	100.0000	0.7982		-	9.6652
Σ				8.9003	23.0869

Fig. 3. Consequence of the automatic interpolation routine for the calculations of the shear strain and stress values at the cross-over (i.e., $G' = G''$). A program-based decision tree transformed the data to linear (lin) and/or logarithmic (log) scales, and then interpolated the data. The derived values are a function of the scales, namely a) lin-lin, b) log-log, c) log-lin, d) lin-log.

Material and Methods

2.1 Soil material and sampling sites

Disturbed soil samples were collected from four topsoil horizons, each representing a textural main class (i.e., sand, silt, clay, and loam, see Table 2 for more details). The sandy reference soil (sand) was excavated from the tilled Ap-horizon of an Arenic Podzol (IUSS WRB, 2014) located in Hodenhagen, Germany. On this soil derived from sandy outwash of the Saale glacier, a potassium (K^+) fertilisation trial had been established in 1989. Sampling took place in October 2014 immediately after maize (*Zea mays* L.) harvest. The silty reference soil (silt) was sampled from a loess-derived Haplic Phaeozem (siltic) at the K^+ fertilisation trial experimental site of the Anhalt University of Applied Sciences in Bernburg, Saxony-Anhalt, Germany, which was established in 1993 on loess-derived soil. Samples were excavated after harvest of spring barley (*Hordeum vulgare* L.) in July 2014. The clayey reference soil (clay) was excavated from superficial horizon of an Oxisol, Typic Hapludox

(USDA, 2014) derived from basaltic rocks and located in Vacaria, Rio Grande do Sul (RS), Brazil.

Table 2. Sand, silt, clay, soil organic carbon (SOC) contents (g kg^{-1} soil⁻¹), pH, of the considered soils.

Textural class	Depth	Sand	Silt	Clay	SOC	pH	Location
	m						
Sand	0 – 0.20	851	99	50	61	4.4	Hodenhagen, Germany
Silt	0 – 0.20	56	719	225	27	7.4	Bernburg, Germany
Loam	0 – 0.20	476	423	101	13	6.1	Cunnersdorf, Germany
Clay	0 – 0.26	71	381	549	34	5.4	Vacaria, Brazil

Sampling took place in July 2013 under cultivated and grazed winter pasture. The loamy reference soil material (loam) was collected from an Eutric Stagnosol derived from sandy loess over Saalean glacial till in Cunnersdorf, Saxony, Germany. Since 1995, the area on the premises of SKW Stickstoffwerke Piesteritz GmbH is subjected to a K^+ fertilisation trial. Sampling took place in August 2016 after the harvest of spring barley (*Hordeum vulgare* L.). For the experimental sites, the plots with K^+ fertilisation, equal to the plant-uptake, were chosen (balanced/optimal fertilisation). Two pits were sampled per sampling site.

2.2 Sample preparation

Air-dried soil was sieved to particle sizes ≤ 2 mm and re-moistened to a gravimetric water content of approximately 10 to 30% depending on clay content and mineralogy. After overnight equilibration, the soil was manually repacked into small cylinders (0.9 cm high and 3.6 cm in diameter) at defined bulk densities, ρ_B , namely, 1.4 Mg m^{-3} for sandy, silty, and loamy soil samples, and 1.1 Mg m^{-3} for clayey samples. Samples were saturated by capillary rise and drained to defined matric potentials, ψ_m , (namely, ψ_m equal to -0 kPa, -3 kPa, -6 kPa, -15 kPa for sandy, silty and loamy samples, and to ψ_m equal to -0 kPa, -3 kPa, -6 kPa, -10 kPa for clayey samples) with the help of ceramic suction plates (for ψ_m equal to -15 kPa) or sand beds (for ψ_m equal to -0 kPa, -3 kPa, -6 kPa).

For sandy, silty, and loamy soils, ten samples, and for the clayey soils three samples per soil material, and matric potential, i.e., 132 samples in total, were cut horizontally in halves to fit the plate-plate gap of 4 mm using a nylon string, as described in Pértile et al. (2018). While the upper halves were used to determine the volumetric water contents, θ , the lower halves were used for the amplitude sweep test after trimming the diameter of the soil sample laterally to 25 mm. Excessive soil material was removed. The water-filled pore space, WFPS (%), was derived from the bulk density, ρ_B (Mg m^{-3}) and the equilibrated water content, θ (Vol.-%), and assuming a specific particle density, ρ_s , of 2.65 Mg m^{-3} (Eq. 10).

$$\text{WFPS (\%)} = \left(1 - \frac{\rho_B}{\rho_s}\right)^{-1} \cdot \theta \quad (\text{Eq. 10})$$

2.3 Amplitude sweep test

Two different modular compact rheometers (both Anton Paar, Stuttgart, Germany) were utilised for the amplitude sweep tests (AST), namely a MCR300 (for sandy, silty and loamy soil samples) and a MCR102 (for clayey soil samples), equipped with identical

measurement systems of profiled parallel plates of 2.5 cm in diameter. For an AST, the soil sample is placed on the lower fixed plate of the rheometer while the upper one is moving in an oscillating (i.e., clock- and counter-clockwise) manner with successively increasing amplitudes at a constant frequency of 0.5 Hz, while a constant temperature of 20 °C was maintained by a Peltier unit. As described by Markgraf et al. (2006), the gap between the plates was set to 4 mm, and the strains are applied in a logarithmic ramp (Fig. 2) with 30 steps and increasing shear strains from 10^{-4} to 100%, resulting in a maximum deflection of the upper plate equal to the height of the gap between the plates in both directions at the end of the test.

2.4 Calculation of the I_z value

I_z was calculated with Eq. 4 and by linearly interpolating the $\tan \delta(n)$ - $\gamma(n)$ relationship for the lower (i.e., $\tan \delta$, at a shear strain, γ_{sp} , equal to 0.001%; Eq. 12) and upper (i.e., $\tan \delta$, at a shear strain, γ_{sp} , equal to 100%; Eq. 12) integration limits.

$$\tan \delta(\gamma_{sp}) = \tan \delta(n-1) + \left(\frac{\tan \delta(n) - \tan \delta(n-1)}{\gamma(n) - \gamma(n-1)} \cdot (\gamma_{sp} - \gamma(n-1)) \right) \quad (\text{Eq. 11})$$

$$\gamma(\tan \delta = 1) = (1 - \tan \delta(n_{max})) \left(\frac{\tan \delta(n_{max}+1) - \tan \delta(n_{max})}{\gamma(n_{max}+1) - \gamma(n_{max})} \right)^{-1} + \gamma_{x_{max}} \quad (\text{Eq. 12})$$

with the measurement point n equal to 1 where $\gamma(n) > \gamma_{sp}$ and $\gamma(n-1) < \gamma_{sp}$ (Fig. 4), and n_{max} equal to the measurement point where $\gamma(n_{max}) < 1$ and $\gamma(n_{max} + 1) > 1$.

Fig. 4. Loss factor $\tan \delta$ as a function of the applied shear strain for measurement points (MP) 1 to 8 with the first three sub-segments of I_z (i.e., $I_z(1)$, $I_z(2)$, $I_z(3)$). See Table 1 for values of $I_z(n)$, $\tan \delta$, and γ .

The values are then integrated as described by Eq. 4. Analogously to Eq. 12, the values of the storage module and shear strain at the cross-over of G' and G'' is calculated.

The R-script attached to this publication (available at <https://github.com/CHaasSoil/IntegralZ>) can be used to derive the values as described above.

2.5 Statistical analysis

The statistical software R (R Development Team, 2021) was used for data processing and visualisation and for linear analysis of regression. The latter one was performed to test if values of either I_Z or ΔI_Z are predictable from covariates, namely, the water-filled pore space, the matric potential, the contents of sand, silt, clay, soil organic carbon and (volumetric) water, and the pH value. The most insignificant covariates were removed stepwise with the model selections until only covariates with a p -value equal to or smaller than 0.05 remained in the models. The values of the shear strain at the cross-over of G' and G'' , and I_Z values were derived with the R-script attached to this publication which utilises the *sfsmisc* package (Maechler, 2021).

Results

Values of I_Z (calculated with the presented R script) ranged from 6.8 to 79.4 and most values were similar to those of I_Z^+ (calculated by *RheoPlus*) (as indicated by the 1:1 line in Fig. 5a) except of some values where I_Z^+ was increased as compared to I_Z . The values of the shear strain at the cross-over as derived with the new approach were either higher or lower compared to the values derived with *RheoPlus* (Fig. 5b).

Fig. 5. a) Integral Z, I_Z^+ , and b) cross-over value, CO^+ , for the textural main classes, as derived with *RheoPlus* as a function of values derived with the new approach with regression lines (red, solid lines), and the line of equality (grey, dashed lines).

Fig. 6. Differences between the values of I_z^+ and I_z (i.e., ΔI_z) as a function of I_z , as defined by Eq. 4, for the textural main classes (columns) and soil matric potentials (ψ_m (kPa); rows), for soil samples with a neglectable deviation (i.e., with a relative deviation (i.e., ΔI_z divided by I_z) smaller than or equal to 5%; green triangles), with a relative deviation larger than 5 and smaller than 10% (orange rectangles), and for samples with a relative deviation of equal to or larger than 10% (red circles).

For most of the considered samples, a neglectable difference between I_z^+ and I_z was found (Fig. 6), because the loss factor values at the ‘cross-over’ (i.e., where G' equals G'') were close to 1, and not significantly altered when set to 1 (as done with the current calculation procedure).

Values of I_z^+ and I_z did not differ for soil samples with loss factor values smaller than 1 in the complete strain range. Considering all samples, the linear regression (Eq. 13) revealed that the values of I_z^+ were overestimated by around 0.71, as expressed by the intercept, b , independently of I_z , as expressed by a value for a of around 1 (Eq. 13, Fig. 5 a, Table 3).

$$I_z^+ = a \cdot I_z + b \quad (\text{Eq. 13})$$

Table 3. Fitting parameters a and b of the linear regression between I_z^+ and I_z (Eq. 13; $I_z^+ = a \cdot I_z + b$), for defined matric potentials, ψ_m , and soil materials with adjusted R^2 , R^2 , and degree of freedom, dF , and p -values.

Soil	ψ_m	a	b	R^2	dF	p -value
All soils	≤ 0	1.003	0.71	0.992	143	<0.0001
	0	1.014	0.25	0.999	31	<0.0001
	-1	0.915	3.77	0.989	4	<0.0001
	-3	0.989	1.26	0.914	34	<0.0001
	-6	1.013	0.39	0.999	32	<0.0001
	≤ -10	1.006	0.53	0.995	68	<0.0001
Sand	0	1.054	-0.30	0.997	7	<0.0001
	-3	0.365	13.87	0.098	8	0.197
	-6	1.061	-0.51	0.986	7	<0.0001
	-15	0.954	2.26	0.990	8	<0.0001
Silt	0	0.983	0.67	0.979	6	<0.0001
	-3	1.038	0.01	0.993	8	<0.0001
	-6	1.037	-0.06	0.997	7	<0.0001
	-15	1.003	0.12	0.995	8	<0.0001
Loam	0	1.161	-1.13	0.995	8	<0.0001
	-3	1.077	-0.27	0.961	8	<0.0001
	-6	1.071	-0.27	0.998	8	<0.0001
	-15	0.897	7.96	0.957	8	<0.0001
Clay	0	0.658	14.24	0.944	1	0.108
	-1	0.708	10.94	0.933	1	0.117
	-3	0.901	4.08	0.924	1	0.124
	-6	1.001	-0.03	1.000	1	0.002
	-10	0.932	3.30	0.980	1	0.063

Similar values for a and b were found when the linear regression is done for each textural main class and matric potential separately (Table 3), except for clay samples due to the lower number in repetitions and for sand samples at matric potential of -3 kPa.

The maximum difference of the absolute values of I_z^+ and I_z , ΔI_z , of around 14.2 was found for a sandy soil sample, equilibrated to a matric potential of -3 kPa, and a value of I_z equal to 8.9 (Fig. 6). For this sample, the values of the parameters at the cross-over (i.e., values as calculated with the new approach and as calculated with *RheoPlus*) did not differ. However, *RheoPlus* set values of $\tan \delta > 1$ to be equal to 1 and integrated the area within the strain range of 0.001% to 100% (Fig. 2, Table 1), which led to an overestimation of I_z^+ of around 160% as compared to I_z . No differences were found for the clayey soil samples from the Typic Hapludox (except for one soil sample equilibrated to a matric potential of -3 kPa (Fig. 6), and for the silty soil samples from the Haplic Phaeozem equilibrated to a matric potential of -15 kPa. For all textures, except for the clayey soil material, values of I_z increased with more negative matric potentials, except for the clayey soil material in which I_z was larger only at matric potential of -6 kPa. For the loamy and silty soil materials, this increase

was most pronounced for samples equilibrated to a matric potential of -15 kPa, while for the sandy soil material, increased values were observed with a matric potential of ≥ -6 kPa.

The model section of linear regression analysis, as described in section 2.5, applied to evaluate the possibility of deriving the value of ΔI_z from soil physical and chemical parameters (Eq. 14), indicated that the value of ΔI_z can be derived just from the sand content, with a p -value of 0.023; R^2 equal to 0.042, and a degree of freedom of 122.

$$\Delta I_z = 0.00099 \cdot \text{sand content} (\text{g kg}^{-1}) + 0.388 \quad (\text{Eq. 14})$$

The results of the model selection for the pedotransfer function, applicable to derive the value of I_z (Eq. 15), revealed, that I_z is a function of soil physical and chemical parameters, namely, the soil matric potential, the water-filled pore space (WFPS), and the contents of soil organic carbon, clay and sand.

$$I_z = a \cdot \Psi_m + b \cdot \text{WFPS} + c \cdot \text{SOC} + d \cdot \text{clay content} + e \cdot \text{sand content} + f \quad (\text{Eq. 15})$$

With fitting parameters, a , b , c , d , e , and intercept f (Table 4), the soil matric potential (Ψ_m in kPa), the water filled pore space, WFPS (%), the soil organic carbon, SOC, clay, and sand contents (g kg^{-1}). For the considered samples, I_z increased with decreasing (i.e., more negative) matric potentials and water-filled pore spaces.

Table 4. Fitting parameters of the model for the prediction of the value of I_z (Eq. 15), with a , b , c , d , and e , reflecting the influences of the matric potential, the water-filled pore space, and the contents of soil organic carbon, clay and silt, and with intercept f , and, fitting parameters a and b reflecting the influences of the clay and sand contents, and intercept c for the prediction of the shear strain (%) at the cross-over (i.e., where G' equals G'' ; Eq. 16).

	Parameter	Value	Std. error	t-value	p-value
I_z	a	-3.44	0.40	-8.68	< 0.0001
	b	0.43	0.14	3.11	0.0024
	c	-0.18	0.08	-2.22	0.0280
	d	0.04	0.01	2.92	0.0043
	e	0.03	0.01	4.75	< 0.0001
	f	-37.35	9.70	-3.85	< 0.0002
Cross-over	a	0.90	0.16	5.66	< 0.0001
	b	0.23	0.07	3.31	0.0012
	c	-185.77	55.01	-3.38	< 0.0001

with a coefficient of determination, R^2 , equal to 0.65, 188 degrees of freedom (dF), and a p -value smaller than 0.0001 for I_z , and, with R^2 equal to 0.21, 121 dF, and a p -value smaller than 0.0001, for the cross-over value.

Following Table 4, increasing SOM contents decreased the value of I_z , but I_z increases with increasing clay and sand contents. This increase is slightly more pronounced for clay as compared to sand (Table 4). The results of the model selection of the pedotransfer function, applicable to derive the value of the shear strain at the cross-over resulted in Eq. 16, based on clay and sand contents:

$$\text{Cross-over} (\%) = a \cdot \text{clay content} + b \cdot \text{sand content} + c \quad (\text{Eq. 16})$$

With fitting parameters, a , b , and intercept c , (Table 4).

Discussion

Calculation errors of values of the Integral Z , I_z , were corrected with the attached R-script. I_z is a summarising parameter and a logarithmic shear strain ramp is applied in the underlying measurement, meaning that the distance between two measurement points increases with increasing shear strains, and therefore, the impact on the value of I_z increases with increasing shear strain. Thus, exact and correct information especially of $\tan \delta$ values at higher strains and of the shear strain at the cross-over of the storage and loss modulus are required. The resulting correlation of I_z and the strain value at the cross-over of the storage and loss moduli, has been pointed out by several studies (e.g., Holthusen et al., 2019; Holthusen et al., 2020; Pértile et al., 2018). That for most measurements no (or a neglectable) difference between the values of the two approaches was found is caused by the soil which remained mostly elastic during the AST and without the occurrence of the cross-over of the storage and loss moduli. Where no cross-over occurs, the previously mentioned errors are avoided and thus, no differences of the two methods are expected. The neglectable differences for the cross-over parameters are possibly caused by varying interpolation routines and rounding errors. Admittedly, the curves of the $\tan \delta$ - γ -relationship shown in Fig. 2a represent an extreme and untypical example, and the value of $\tan \delta$ larger than 2 is probably a measuring error, and thus, not very trustworthy. This measurement was not considered in the framework where it had been measured but was identified as measuring error by Heibach (2018). Still, this curve is helpful to impressively demonstrate the calculation errors, which more than doubled the value of the integrated area.

Similar to previous studies (e.g., Stoppe 2015; Stoppe and Horn, 2018), the pedotransfer function indicates that I_z can be derived from soil physical and chemical parameters, reflecting the impact of the soil structure (here, in terms of the soil matric potential and the water-filled pore space), the SOC content, and the soil texture (namely, the sand and clay contents). The stabilising effect of a more negative soil matric potential is well-proven for the considered matric potential range (i.e., 0. to -15 kPa, Pértile et al., 2016) and reference soil materials (except for sandy soil) at the soil core-scale and coincides with a decreasing water-filled pore space. This stabilising mechanism is based on the occurrence of water menisci pulling primary particles together due to the contracting force (caused by the surface tension of the soil pore water), as described by the effective strain Equation (as described e.g., in Horn 2003). However, a change in the shape of the water menisci from concave to convex, e.g., due to shearing forces applied with an AST results in the total loss of the mechanical soil stability by a declining angle of the internal friction.

The mechanical stability of soils is increased by gluing agents like lime, iron oxides, and organic exudates (Haas et al. 2018a) or soil organic matter (SOM) contents in general (Batistão et al., 2020; Pértile et al., 2018). In this study, gluing agents like iron oxides, lime, or biological exudates were not considered, however, the pH value which indicates the presence of lime, was not identified as factor with significant impact on the value of I_z . The pH values of the considered reference materials were acidic (pH equal to 4.4) to neutral (pH equal to 7.4). While at neutral pH values Ca^{2+} bridges stabilise the primary particles, Al^{3+} contributes to the soil aggregate stability at acidic soil conditions. A decreased soil aggregate stability can be expected within pH values from 5-6.5, due to the absence of both, Ca^{2+} and Al^{3+} bridges.

Contrastingly to the findings of other authors (e.g., Khaidapova et al., 2016), SOM was found to decrease the soil aggregate stability, and consequently, the value of I_z , which indicates a soil loosening effect of SOM at the particle-particle-scale. If hydrophilic, SOM is known to increase the water content at any given matric potential which affects the Chi factor described in the effective stress equation of Bishop (1960). In our experiments, however, defined samples with defined bulk densities were investigated which results in, increasing values for the water-filled pore space with increasing SOM contents. Thus, if shearing forces are applied in the AST, positive water pressures are expected to occur with less intense shearing forces for samples rich in SOM as compared to samples low in SOM, due to an increased ratio of water-filled pores spaces, leading to soil liquification. This generalisation is however critical because SOM is a heterogeneous mixture of organic components containing hydrophilic (C=O) and hydrophobic (C-H) functional groups in varying ratios. The wettability of soils is reduced with increasing ratios of hydrophobic functional groups (Haas et al. 2018b), and a hydrophobicity in soils can persist for several weeks, as shown by Woche et al. (2015).

In previous studies, I_z^+ was used to derive pedotransfer function (Stoppe, 2015) or to identify single stages of thixotropy in allophanic Andosols (Baumgarten et al., 2013). The quality of these studies is not diminished, because the calculation error led to overestimations of the value of I_z but can be easily corrected by applying the attached R-script. However, the calculations by *RheoPlus* resulted in over- and underestimated values of the shear strain at the cross-over, thus, studies focusing on the cross-over value may be more prone to errors. The pedotransfer function for the prediction of the shear strain at the cross-over is not applicable for parameter estimation as indicated by a low value of the coefficient of determination. Following this model, increasing shear stresses at the cross-over of G' and G'' can be expected for silty > sandy > clayey soils, as indicated by the slopes of regression coefficients, for any given value of the soil matric potential or, e.g., the WFPS. That solely the sand content can be used to derived to ΔI_z from covariates (i.e., physical and chemical soil parameters) as indicated by the linear model is questionable, since ΔI_z is not only based on mechanical processes but also on calculation errors due to wrong settings in the used software. This is also reflected by the low value of the degree of determination, R^2 , (i.e., 0.04), indicating the weaknesses of the model. In conclusion, using a pedotransfer function in order to correct data previously proceeded by the standard *RheoPlus* procedure, might lead to less accurate and representative values than re-calculating the values of I_z and of the cross-over.

Conclusion

Pedotransfer functions were derived to estimate the values of the summarising soil quasi-elasticity parameter, I_z , and of the shear strain at which the cross-over of the loss and storage moduli occurred from soil physical and chemical parameters. Presuming that parameters like the water-filled pore space, the initial matric potential, and SOM, clay, and sand contents are known, the quasi-elasticity can be satisfyingly estimated. The pedotransfer functions indicate that the microstructural soil stability bases on soil hydraulics, soil texture and SOM content.

Results of the two calculation approaches were compared and a maximum deviation between I_z and values calculated by *RheoPlus*, I_z^+ , of up to 160% was found for a sandy

sample from the tilled A-horizon of an arenic Podzol, equilibrated to a matric potential of -3 kPa. For most of the considered samples, a neglectable method-based difference for I_z was found, because the loss factor values at the ‘cross-over’ (i.e., where G' equals G'') were close to 1, and not significantly altered when set to 1 (as done with the current calculation procedure). No method-based difference was found for soil samples with loss factor values smaller than 1 in the complete strain range. For the cross-over values both slightly over- and underestimated values were found with the *RheoPlus* approach and might bias data. The attached script, written in the environment of the open-source software R, can be used to rapidly and correctly calculate I_z , and the cross-over parameters by linearly scaling the storage and loss modulus versus shear strain relationships. In further research, the soil matric potential dynamics and the soil wettability should be considered to better understand the deformation behaviour of soils and the interaction effects of soil mechanics and soil hydraulics.

Acknowledgements

The authors P. Heibach and D. Holthusen are thankful for the financial support received from the K+S Kali GmbH (Kassel) for their doctoral studies that supplied part of the data utilised in the present paper. Furthermore, P. Pértile would like to acknowledge the Coordination for the Improvement of Higher Education Personnel CAPES (Brazil, finance code 001) and the National Council for Scientific and Technological Development CNPq (Brazil) for the scholarship granted to her for the evaluation of the Brazilian soil data.

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